

THE ROLE OF INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES TEACHING ENGLISH LANGUAGES

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Abstract. *Technology is no longer a fringe course enhancement, of interest to only enthusiastic technophile' teachers, learners and managers, but rather, it has an importance for everyone concerned in language teaching. The area of technology-enhanced language learning is highly controversial; there are so many ways of looking at technology in teaching. This paper explores opportunities that English teachers have created to help students meet English language literacy goals in technology enhanced language learning classroom environments.*

Keywords: *modern innovative technologies, requires, activity, processes, products, actions, important, discussion, debates, rational, motivation, technical support.*

РОЛЬ ИННОВАЦИОННЫХ ТЕХНОЛОГИЙ В ОБУЧЕНИИ АНГЛИЙСКОМУ ЯЗЫКУ

Аннотация. *Технология больше не является второстепенным усовершенствованием курса, представляющим интерес только для увлеченных технофилов-учителей, учащихся и менеджеров, а, скорее, имеет значение для всех, кто занимается преподаванием языков. Область изучения языков с помощью технологий вызывает большие споры; существует так много способов взглянуть на технологии в обучении. В этой статье исследуются возможности, созданные учителями английского языка, чтобы помочь учащимся достичь целей по обучению английскому языку в учебной среде с улучшенными технологиями.*

Ключевые слова: *современные инновационные технологии, потребности, деятельность, процессы, продукты, действия, важные, обсуждение, дебаты, рациональные, мотивация, техническое обеспечение.*

The development of the education system requires that pedagogical science and practice study and introduce new methods of teaching and raising children. Innovations in pedagogy connect with general processes in society, global problems, integration of knowledge and forms of social being.

Technology is theoretically neutral, but a teaching activity:

(1) reflects a theory of teaching, learning, and foreign language learning of the designer and/or instructor (2) reflects a theory of technology as:

Drillmaster: behaviorist

Tutor: cognitive

Tool: constructivist

Mediator: socio-cultural

Part of an ecology: socio-cognitive

A TELL activity has **goals** and **objectives** like any other language learning activity It can be **integral** or **peripheral** to the lesson or curriculum. It an integrate **skills** or treat them separately

A requires instructor technological literacy, requires (but can also develop) student technological literacy, requires class access to technology, sometimes requires technical support

During a teaching activity, the instructor may be monitoring, guiding, facilitating, assisting, and evaluating, the students may be working individually, in pairs, or in groups, the students are clicking, dragging, and scrolling, but also listening, speaking, reading, and writing

A teaching activity has processes, products, and actions that can be assessed. These should be assessed in a way that matches the activity objectives and approach

A teaching activity should be evaluated during and after implementation. It can be altered during implementation based on evaluation to meet student needs. It reflects principles of language learning

Using teaching provides a lot more flexibility and caters to more learning styles of the language learners compared to traditional styles of teaching.

TELL can be used alongside textbooks for a much more in depth learning experience

TELL turns the classroom into a student centred environment. Students can:

Select order in which material is presented to them (ex. grammar program first and vocabulary building game last)

Control the material presented to them (ex. Visit the Coliseum in Rome, Italy on CD-ROM or learn about the 2006 Olympics in Torino, Italy)

Control the pace of progress (ex. students can work through level 1 & 2 on grammar today and then level 1 on vocabulary the following day)

TELL improves motivation and develops better attitudes in students towards learning.

Learning is not confined to the area within the classroom environment, it is enlarged. Students can learn about language at home and practice language in class.

Disadvantages of teaching

Cost of technology

Cost of training

Cost of media

Teacher or instructor must be comfortable with using technology

Technology not 100% fault proof

Access issues outside the classroom

Problem of too much work done by the computer. The language student must not rely entirely on the help system of language software to guide them through exercises but must make conscious effort to attempt exercises for a better learning experience.

Main types of media using technology teaching

1. Sound (audio)

Radio broadcasts

Recorded playback of speeches

Recorded storytelling

2. Films (video + audio)

Short films

Interviews

Full length full feature movies

3. Images/Graphics

Charts

Paintings

Photos

4. Texts

Essays

Journals

Articles

Email

Chatting

Books

Now a new pedagogy is creating, a characteristic feature of which is innovation - the ability to renew, openness to new things. It is known by the innovation process is a complex activity for the creation, assimilation, use and dissemination of innovations. In order to arouse students' interest in learning a foreign language, we, teachers of English, should look for new, interesting and effective forms and methods of teaching. During the period of study you need to use such methods in which: students have a desire for creative, productive work; students become active, relaxed, trying to succeed, while not violating classroom behavior. The specificity of a foreign language as an academic subject is that communication is not only the ultimate goal of learning, but also a means of achieving it. The teacher who does everything possible and impossible for this. Since speech remains the only universal base of thinking, knowledge of a foreign language should be considered from the point of view of improving intellectual abilities (memory, imagination, critical, logical, creative thinking). Creativity is the highest manifestation of the development of the human mind. Creative ability is the ability to wonder, learn, the ability to find solutions in unusual situations, it is a focus on the discovery of new things and the ability to have a deep awareness of one's experience. Thanks to the creative activity of the child develops the ability to realize independently their potential, self-realization leads to personal growth. The implementation of this idea is impossible without the development and implementation of appropriate learning technologies. The school should be life. This can achieve through an innovative approach, creating an interactive environment. The word interactive (translated from English and "mutual", act - "to act") means interaction. The interactive method is a way to interact with students through conversation, dialogue. Interactive learning is learning in a dialogue mode, during which the participants in the pedagogical process interact with the goal of mutual understanding, jointly solving learning tasks, and developing the personal qualities of students. 90 It is important for a modern teacher to know the newest methods of teaching a foreign language, special educational technologies and techniques in order to optimally choose one or another teaching method in accordance with the level of knowledge, needs and interests of students. Rational and motivated use of teaching methods in the classroom in a foreign language requires a creative approach on the part of the teacher. High-quality language training of students is impossible without the use of modern innovative educational technologies. Modern innovative technologies in education are the use of information and communication technologies in teaching, employment in training, working with educational computer and multimedia programs, distance technologies in teaching foreign languages, creating presentations in the Microsoft PowerPoint software environment, using the resources of the worldwide Internet. These technologies provide an individualization and differentiation of education, taking into account the abilities of children, their level of knowledge. To achieve

communicative competence - communicative skills formed to the basis of language knowledge, skills and abilities - I use the latest teaching methods that combine communicative and cognitive goals. Innovative methods of teaching foreign languages, based on an innovative approach, aimed at the development and self-improvement of the individual, on the disclosure of its reserve capabilities and creative potential. The main principles of modern methods: movement from the whole to the private, orientation of the classes to the student, purposefulness and pithiness of the classes, their focus on achieving social interaction if the teacher has faith in the success of his students, integrating the language and learning it through knowledge from other fields of science.

Modern communicative methods offer a widespread introduction into the educational process of active nonstandard methods and forms of work for better conscious learning of the material. In practice, such forms of work turned out to be quite effective: individual, pair, group and teamwork. Modern technologies include the technology of cooperation. The main idea is to create conditions for active joint activity of students in various educational situations.

Children unite in groups of 3-4 people, they have given one task, and the role of each has discussed. Each student is responsible not only for the result of his work, but also for the result of the whole group. Therefore, weak students try to find out from the strong that which is incomprehensible to them, and the strong - so that the weak understand the task. The whole class will benefit from this, as they jointly eliminate gaps in knowledge. During various types of work, students face with the problem of increasing their knowledge, vocabulary or communication skills, so they activate their activities and, in the process of communication, try to solve these issues.

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Therefore, all exercises and tasks should be communicatively justified by the lack of information, choice and response (Information gap, choice, feedback). For their implementation, students will need additional information and make some efforts to achieve it, and thus will be able to better and more effectively organize their activities. The most effective forms of steam and group work: • internal (external) circles (inside / outside circles); • brainstorming (brain storm); • zigzag reading (jigsaw reading); • exchange of views (think-pair-share); • pair interviews and others. These forms of work contribute to the expansion of knowledge and skills of students. In the process of communication, students learn to solve complex problems based on the analysis of relevant information, to express alternative opinions, to make informed decisions, to communicate with different people, to participate in discussions.

One of the technologies providing student-centered learning is the project method as a way to develop creative, cognitive activity and independence. Projects can be subdivided into mono-projects, collective, oral-language, written and Internet projects. Work on the project is a multi-level approach to learning the language, covering reading, listening, speaking and grammar. The project method contributes to the development of active independent thinking among students and orients them towards joint research work.

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